

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges

**Document: D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and
Engagement Plan (Final)**

30/04/2021

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D10.4		
Deliverable Title	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan		
Due Date	30-Apr-2021	Delivery Date	17-Jun-2021
Lead Beneficiary	RICOH (12)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	INAF (3)		
Editor(s)	Daniel Martínez (RICOH), Javier Ramirez (RICOH)		
Authors (s)	Daniel Martínez (RICOH) Javier Ramirez (RICOH)		
Contributor (s)	Eva Sciacca, Filomena Bufano, Cristobal Bordiu (INAF)		
Reviewer(s)	Cristobal Bordiu (INAF)		
Workpackage No	WP10 Communication, Dissemination & Outreach		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Feedback
Distribution	Public	Type	DEC
Keywords	EOSC, Security, Underwater Research, Planetary Science, Astrophysics, Atmospheric Research, Web Site, Dissemination, Strategy		

Change Record

Version	Date	Description	Editor
1	17-06-2021	Document version submitted to EC	Daniel Martínez (RICOH)

Disclaimer

NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, via grant agreement No. 863448.

NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

This document has been produced supported by receiving funding from the European Commission. The content of this document is a product of the NEANIAS project Consortium, and it does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The editor, author, contributors and reviewers of this document have taken all any available measures to ensure that in order for its content is to be accurate and lawful. However, neither the project

consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document may be held responsible for any damage, financial or other loss or any other issue that may arise as a result of using the content of this document or any of the project outputs that this document may refer to.

The European Union (EU) was established in accordance with the Treaty on the European Union (Maastricht). There are currently 28 member states of the European Union. It is based on the European Communities and the member states' cooperation in the fields of Common Foreign and Security Policy and Justice and Home Affairs. The five main institutions of the European Union are the European Parliament, the Council of Ministers, the European Commission, the Court of Justice, and the Court of Auditors (<http://europa.eu.int/>).

Table of Contents

Document Info	2
Change Record	3
Disclaimer	4
Table of Contents	5
Tables of Figures & Tables	7
Abstract	9
1. Introduction	10
1.1. Background and context	10
1.2. Structure of the document.....	10
2. Objectives and approach	12
3. Communication & Dissemination Strategy	15
3.1. Project identity	15
3.2. Target audience.....	16
3.2.1. <i>Segmentation analysis from a field of activity perspective</i>	16
3.2.2. <i>Segmentation analysis from a profile/needs perspective</i>	17
3.3. Key messages	18
3.4. Engagement plan.....	20
3.5. Promotion of digital dissemination	21
4. Methodology	26
4.1. Dissemination Principles	26
4.2. Content generation	26
4.2.1. <i>Presentations</i>	26
4.2.2. <i>Digital channels</i>	27
4.2.3. <i>Contents of general purpose</i>	27
4.2.4. <i>Contents of technical purpose</i>	27
4.3. Dissemination & Communication instruments	27
4.3.1. <i>Wide range</i>	27
4.3.2. <i>Ecosystem</i>	33
4.3.3. <i>Project resources for partners</i>	38
4.4. Instrument per line of activity	40
4.4.1. <i>Communication instruments</i>	41
4.4.2. <i>Dissemination instruments</i>	41
4.5. Cross promotion.....	41
5. Organization	46
5.1. Coordination Model	46

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

5.2.	Coordination activities	47
5.2.1.	<i>WP 10 working group</i>	47
5.2.2.	<i>WP 10 Committee</i>	48
5.2.3.	<i>Project meetings</i>	48
5.2.4.	<i>On demand meetings</i>	48
5.3.	Key Performance Indicator	49
5.4.	Roles	51
5.5.	Monitoring and Evaluation	51
5.5.1.	<i>Digital channels</i>	51
5.5.2.	<i>Physical channels</i>	52
5.5.3.	<i>Reporting models</i>	53
6.	Planning	55
6.1.	Deliverables Description	55
6.2.	Deliverables Planning	55
6.3.	Timeline	56
	List of acronyms	57

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

Figure 1. NEANIAS updated official logo.	15
Figure 2. NEANIAS logos for thematic services	15
Figure 3. NEANIAS Open Call.	16
Figure 4. Application of templates for NEANIAS Open Call.....	16
Figure 5. NEANIAS team interacting and promoting the project.....	21
Figure 6. NEANIAS twitter account, connecting to NEANIAS ecosystem.....	22
Figure 7. Interaction with other projects and the ecosystem.	22
Figure 8. Online participation at congress.	23
Figure 9. Promoting a NEANIAS digital event on Twitter.....	24
Figure 10. Events register on NEANIAS website.....	24
Figure 11. Knowing our audience: subscription form to NEANIAS newsletter.	25
Figure 12. NEANIAS website (home page).....	29
Figure 13. NEANIAS, LinkedIn group.	30
Figure 14. NEANIAS account in twitter.....	30
Figure 15. NEANIAS account in Facebook.....	31
Figure 16. NEANIAS channel for YouTube.	31
Figure 17. NEANIAS, some samples of dissemination material.	32
Figure 18. NEANIAS, material for project identity.....	33
Figure 19. First NEANIAS Open Call announcement	36
Figure 20. Hackathons celebrate at the Blue Days Event.....	36
Figure 21. NEANIAS project meeting. Family photo with the old project banner.	37
Figure 22. NEANIAS banner welcoming the project Meeting.....	37
Figure 23. Available material for NEANIAS project meeting.	38
Figure 24. NEANIAS online meetings.....	38
Figure 25. NEANIAS template for presentation.	40
Figure 26. NEANIAS brochure.	40
Figure 27. NEANIAS channels and contact points from the website.....	42
Figure 28. NEANIAS twitter account with the connection to NEANIAS website.....	42
Figure 29. NEANIAS presentation with references to social channels	43
Figure 30. NEANIAS reference from partner's website.....	43
Figure 31. NEANIAS reference from CORDIS Europe.	44
Figure 32. NEANIAS reference from the European Open Science Cloud site.....	44
Figure 33. NEANIAS website and connection to other sites.	45
Figure 34. Coordination model.	46
Figure 35. Dissemination and KPIs assignments process.	46
Figure 36 Redmine application	47
Figure 37. NEANIAS Facebook account: tracking facilities (example).	52
Figure 38. Timeline	56

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Document Tables

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination, engagement and outreach approach.	12
Table 2. Target audience and key messages.	20
Table 3. Digital resources for project partners.	39
Table 4. KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction.	49
Table 5. KPIs concerning innovation dissemination.	49
Table 6. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination.	50
Table 7. KPIs concerning social dissemination.	50
Table 8. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts.	51
Table 9. Outreach Task Force members.	52
Table 10. Dissemination planning.	56

Abstract

NEANIAS is an ambitious project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the recent ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. NEANIAS will drive the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. Each of these sectors considers a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies. Each thematic service will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. In doing so, NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities.

As stated above, one of the key tasks in the project is to communicate and disseminate the developments, outputs and benefits of NEANIAS to a wide spectrum of stakeholders in order to get their involvement and engagement, facilitating so the achievement of the objectives set. This task must be implemented taking into account different profiles, needs, interests, areas of application and each kind of relationship with the project.

This document is a reviewed and improved version of the first report already submitted as “Deliverable D10.1 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft)” on the 2nd month of the project and aimed to define the project Communication, Dissemination and Outreach goals and to describe the overall plan for the entire project duration.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and context

This document is a reviewed and improved version of the first report already submitted as “Deliverable D10.1 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft)” on the 2nd month of the project.

The draft plan exposed the vision, strategy, and a final plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes and baseline dissemination material related to the NEANIAS project. This plan presented the roadmap to drive the most out of the project effort in the direction of (i) bringing its results to the wider and most appropriate audience that will be interested or motivated in exploiting or uptaking it and (ii) engaging stakeholders into project’s activities and paving the road for adoption and establishing strong synergies.

The plan refines the project strategy, with respect to overall objective, scope and targeted stakeholders (and the related sub-objectives and means for each target) and then lay out the resource allocation plan and key points in time for Communication and outreach activities, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, liaison activities and knowledge transfer.

The current updated final plan is aligned with the original plan, both in the strategic lines and in the material and personal means employed. The work has been carried out as expected, with a great contingency that had to be solved: the pandemic of COVID-19 hit the world since March 2020, just few months after the NEANIAS started. The world slowed down, the economy fell, the priorities of companies and organizations changed abruptly, health practically monopolized new investments in research, and people had to fight against new adversities, including personal and health problems.

Face-to-face activities were suspended (events, fairs, congresses, exhibitions, meetings, ...) and online activities were gradually promoted as an alternative. These circumstances had an obvious impact on the WP10 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement. But despite the uncertainty and all the adversities, the project was resilient and the team’s capacity to adapt was noteworthy, so that it adapted to the new casuistry as the needs required. This document reflects the lessons learned and updates the action plan to a new reality that, despite health progress and the development of vaccines, still maintains many uncertainties regarding the possibility to organize face-to-face activities.

1.2. Structure of the document

From this point, the current document is organized according the following structure and contents:

1. **Objectives and approach:** Introduction to the objectives of the dissemination, communication and outreach plan and its approach for its consequent development.
2. **Dissemination strategy.** As a preliminary step, communication, dissemination, outreach and engagement strategy is set, considering first the consolidation of the project identity,

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

target audience definition as a previous step to organize the key messages to communicate to the audience and the engagement plan for the stakeholders.

3. **Methodology.** The development of methodology section is the main part of the document, starting with the dissemination principles before continuing with the process for the generation of contents and the tools, resources and means to carry out dissemination activities, both at a wide range and for ecosystem scope. Lastly, the project resources for partners are presented.
4. **Organization.** The organization section presents the coordination model, the roles of the project partners and the monitoring and evaluation method, including the definition of KPIs.
5. **Planning.** Finally, an activity timeline is presented.

2. Objectives and approach

The objectives of the NEANIAS communication, dissemination, and user engagement activities and how they will be implemented are described in the following table below.

Type of Activity	NEANIAS Objectives	Means and Activities
Communication	1. Increase NEANIAS visibility in terms of activities and outcomes; receive valuable feedback	Communication effort aiming at the targeted multiple audience beyond NEANIAS community; Exploit feedback and ameliorate services strengthening potentials and exploitation
	2. Inform Society and Enhance Market-uptake for the developed EOSC Services	Communicate project outcomes at broad, diverse audience. Targeted communication efforts towards potential users of and beyond the considered thematic sectors.
Dissemination	3. Position NEANIAS as a top-rank EU EOSC project and EOSC Services Hub	Dense dissemination activities linked to the pre- and post- launch of the foreseen EOSC Services to promote them during their operational phase within the considered sectors and EOSC community.
	4. Boost commercial exploitation strategy of the deployed EOSC services	Targeted and synchronized dissemination, communication, exploitation and user engagement activities aiming towards all target audiences and policymakers.
User Engagement and Outreach	5. Share knowledge for further development and optimization of the considered services	Early co-design, agile development along with dissemination and targeted user engagement activities aiming at primary target audiences.
	6. Raise awareness and demonstrate how NEANIAS services can cater to the needs and thematic end-user requirements	Communication efforts along with carefully designed activities for maximizing impact including hands-on training of several primary targeted audiences.

Table 1. Communication, Dissemination, engagement and outreach approach.

Particularly the WP aims to:

- establish a visual and textually recognizable impression of the project and its work.
- maximize the impactful visibility of project's work and achievements.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- engage stakeholders that can support project sustainability through both update and feedback and can further empower the vision around EOSC and Open Science.
- provide essential information and knowledge on the NEANIAS project to 3rd parties activating esp. in the H2020 and EOSC landscape.
- be the updated repository of all dissemination activities carried out in the project: publication of articles, call for or participation in events, collaboration with other projects, etc.

Its achievement will be led by Outreach Task Force (OTF) (see proposal, Grant Agreement, D1.2), with the support of Project Management Board and the participation of all project members according to their knowledge, their area of expertise, and their networking. The goals have to be reached in a collaborative way under common strategy, so critical tasks of the Outreach Task force (OTF) will be to provide project members with the main resources to facilitate its activities and to encourage the members to work together.

The approach can be summarized under the following 9 premises:

- **Announce NEANIAS to the scientific community:** it needs to properly explain the NEANIAS's vision and strategy, identify key target (ICT & researchers) and define content and channels for each target.
- **Partners, the first believers, first users and first promoters.** It is necessary to gain the engagement of the partners (by means of internal communication) and to take advantage of each partner's knowledge and contacts to boost their best contributions. A recurrent task of enhancing and sharing of synergies will drive to the best achievements.
- **Understand the real needs of end users:** to get the deepest understanding of real needs is necessary to enable and promote 2-way communication channels. Events (and specifically those related to innovation, such as Open Call and Hackathons) and the digital channels are a good way to achieve this.
- **Tune the offer:** in order to define values services and solution, we need to transfer to the offering the identified needs. A close contact with the ecosystem is a key work to do it.
- **Boost the demand:** By means of a close access to the end user, Identification of use cases, and dissemination of content and benefits.
- **Knowledge hub:** Content and knowledge repository of the partners implies coordination of any news, content or achievement, and its later dissemination and storage.
- **Measurement & Control:** No achievement can be made without its measurement and control, both for reporting purpose and for gamification tactics in order to strengthen the recurrent collaboration among all the partners. The distribution and assignment of tasks is a key point to achieve it efficiently
- **Consortium cooperation.** Thematic partners are the ones who can best understand the real needs of the sector and those who can best present the new solutions that NEANIAS is developing for them. In addition, their network is an asset in attracting

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

and engaging the ecosystem, including the ability to publish scientific and technical content, both on the NENIAS website and in prestigious media and magazines.

- **The potential of digital channels:** In times of a global pandemic, where face-to-face activities are severely restricted, digital channels have proven to be the best way to attract and maintain an engaged audience, both thematic and general. Its enhancement and use are considered key to maximize the communication and the dissemination of project activities, as well as a valuable platform for engagement purposes.

3. Communication & Dissemination Strategy

3.1. Project identity

In order to get a recognizable NEANIAS brand, a project identity and graphic charter have been developed. As commented in D10.1, changes on the brand image were possible during the first months of the project under internal contest between all partners of the consortium. The result is an updated logo that has been applied to all project templates, both for internal and external communication and dissemination actions. This new brand image is presented below.

Figure 1. NEANIAS updated official logo.

The project identity relates to the appearance and visibility of a project for any stakeholder and applies to any document or resource created (both electronic and printed). This includes the logo, the colour gamut, the typography and page compositions. Its application is required for any document (project deliverables, power point presentation, leaflets, brochures, ...), the web site or the social media banners. A set of templates and a book of style for different purposes have been created and shared with all the project partners to homogenize the project outputs. In addition, any product or reusable material related to NEANIAS project (banners, notebooks, ...) will be designed including the logo and NEANIAS patterns.

Following the styles of NEANIAS, the thematic services also have their own image, as shown below.

Figure 2. NEANIAS logos for thematic services

Besides the three high-level themed logos for Submarine, Atmospheric and Space, each service has its own logo. Furthermore, a dedicated design can be produced for promote featured events such as the NEANIAS Open Call or the project hackathons.

Figure 3. NEANIAS Open Call.

Figure 4. Application of templates for NEANIAS Open Call.

3.2. Target audience

As innovative thematic services are going to be co-designed with specific user communities addressing real, current needs and requirements, the target user must be previously identified. They are segmented from their field of activity (sector) as well as the different profiles of user.

3.2.1. Segmentation analysis from a field of activity perspective

From the sector / business perspective, there are three thematic sectors plus the transversal ICT, among which we can identify the real end users.

- For the Underwater sector: archaeologists, geologists, oil & gas engineers, renewable energy planners, robotics, submarine geohazards, insurance companies.
- For the Atmospheric sector: geologists, urban air quality authorities, meteorological services, energy and power sector, industrial air pollutant emitters, ecologists, rural urban planners, geohazards, civil protection, insurance, health.
- For the Space sector: astrophysics scientists, planetary scientists, planetary mining engineers, planetary robotics, mobile telecommunications, space weather, space upstream engineers.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- For ICT sector: Core-services platforms providers, and engineers in a wide range of activities such as signal processing, virtual and augmented reality, graphics management (capture, management and analysis), computer vision, machine learning, software development.

This segmentation will allow us to identify the best WP thematic from which to know, understand and connect with the needs of the audience in order to expose closely the use cases and services.

3.2.2. Segmentation analysis from a profile/needs perspective

In addition to the sector and business perspective, it is needed to set the particular profile of stakeholders in order to understand the real needs and potential engagement with the project, as well as the key message definition to reach them in the best way.

The preliminary segmentation considers the following profiles, defining their needs and potential connection to NEANIAS:

- **Researchers:** Individual researchers are easier to mobilize on a personal basis through project offerings, support for penetration into scientific communities and provide valuable feedback. They also provide gateways to larger groups and other disciplines.
- **Research groups:** Research groups are the intended main target group of the project, for reusing and interweaving the service and data offerings to be generated. They are a major provider of validation information and feedback, as well as the drivers of interdisciplinary research targeted by the project.
- **Academic institutes:** Academic institutes can form an application space where thematic services can be utilized in the field of education, in labs and lesson courses.
- **Data providers:** Data providers can greatly enrich the project offering regarding data intensive services adding to the value chain and business and sustainability opportunities.
- **Service Providers:** Service providers can be either consumers or suppliers of elements for the service stack project, adding to the value chain and business and sustainability opportunities.
- **Open Access/Open Science Initiatives:** Open access/Open Science initiatives provide guidance, support, validation and assets that can be reused in the context of the Project.
- **Business SMEs:** SMEs providing business services on top of research data and services are one of the best options for creating generating value chains on top of project offerings an essential part of sustainability targets.
- **E-Infrastructure, EOSC (hub) satellite projects:** The EU project landscape has several opportunities for reuse of data, services and knowhow, and needs to be closely monitored, contacted and informed about the project activities.
- **(Digital) Innovation Hubs / Business Clusters:** Aggregators of business and innovation are a source of potential adopters and uptakers as well as of ideas for new business cases not initially considered.
- **Governmental Entities and Other Public Sector Bodies:** Governance and policy making is essential target group of the project, and substantially adds to the sustainability outlook.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- **Funders:** Funders' awareness is a great means of validation and is also an essential part of the project's obligations.
- **Press, media and disseminators:** Anyone will be able to find more information and learn more about NEANAS if our services and solutions are presented and discussed in other media. Arousing the interest of magazines or technical journals (both print and online) and even on digital platforms, are very interesting for our purposes.
- **General Public:** The project is also addressed to the general public, including any audience not mentioned above, such as journalist, students, scientist, or the society in a broad sense.

3.3. Key messages

The messages to generate must be tailored to any individual segment, highlighting the specific benefits of the project for each one, in order to favour its reception. Besides, the language and context must be aligned with the perspective of their field of activity exposed above.

The main benefits to expose are the following:

Profile	Benefits to communicate
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadening the user base. • Indirect raising of awareness. • Enabling of new (interdisciplinary) research opportunities. • Availability of enhanced tools for researching. • Facilitation of focus on core activities. • New ways of collaboration.
Research groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadening user base. • Indirect raising of awareness. • Provisioning of structured feedback. • Identification and enabling of new (inter-disciplinary) research opportunities. • Availability of enhanced tools for researching. • Facilitation of focus on core activities.
Academic institutes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broadening user base. • Expanding business opportunities. • New opportunities of collaboration. • Availability of channels for promotion and dissemination.
Data providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of data enabled service offerings. • New opportunities for research. • Expanding business opportunities. • Resolution of data outage/access restriction/data quality issues.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Service Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of service-based value chain. • Reuse of existing systems. • New business opportunities. • Empowering of sustainability.
Open Access/ Open Science Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project awareness support. • Validation and feedback acquisition. • Embracing open science. • Validation and feedback acquisition. • Availability of new channels for promotion and dissemination. • New ways of collaboration.
Business SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowering of sustainability options. • New business opportunities. • Access to new fields and ecosystems.
e-Infrastructure, EOSC (hub) satellite projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service reuse and a common challenge confronting for effort optimization. • Amplification of outreach. • Identification of new (inter-disciplinary) research opportunities and service value chains. • Improving specific knowledge in thematic sectors.
(Digital) Innovation Hubs / Business Clusters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowering of sustainability options. • New business opportunities. • Expanding an adoption base. • Improving specific knowledge in thematic sectors.
Governance & Policy Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion to new business cases. • Widening of sustainability options. • Empowerment of research. • New opportunities for helping the collaboration, facilitating the focus on strategic / core sectors. • Availability of new KPIs.
Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation and feedback. • Amplification of outreach. • Supporting/validating sustainability.
Press & Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirect raising of awareness. • New business opportunities. • Access to new fields and ecosystems. • Expanding an adoption base. • Improving specific knowledge in thematic sectors.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the value of project and individual partners. • General information according to transparency principles.
----------------	---

Table 2. Target audience and key messages.

3.4. Engagement plan

The dissemination activities are led by the Outreach Task Force (OTF), but all the partners are required to obtain the best achievements. The aim is to maximize their knowledge, experience and networking concerning to each of their specific area of expertise, both in different fields (underwater, atmospheric, space, ICT, innovation, market and business, ...) and countries. Working together, the range and impact of any dissemination action will be empowered to its highest degree.

The key action is to consolidate an engagement plan that will drive all the project members to actively participate in the dissemination activities.

The following aspects are considered key, and will be reviewed and enhanced during the project life:

- Best practices guides: Development of a guide of best practices to encourage the partners to take advantage of available resources (NEANIAS portal, partner’s web site, digital social platforms, reusable material, ...) to boost the results of the dissemination activities.

The guidelines, consisting of any executive document for specific purpose, will be dynamically developed, presented and shared on the project platform. These documents can also be generated as a response to a requirement as well as considering a specific need of the project development.

- Team building: Keeping partners aligned with common goals will allow us to be synchronized in the activities, sharing contents and produced material, sharing lessons learnings, saving efforts and acting in a similar way in different fields, context and countries.

This will also drive us to better identify and manage any potential risk or contingency, allocating resources and solutions as best suits.

The project meetings, the internal mailings, social platforms and digital channels including the web site will be appropriate to get it.

- Fields of knowledge: the project involves many content from different fields of knowledge, which is necessary to allow an easy understanding of all the stakeholders and even the members of the consortium.

Some activities and generation of content need to be performed by a particular partner (specifically those concerning to thematic fields) in order to identify, produce, and validate its suitability and quality and to suggest the best thematic channels and scenarios to disseminate. The impact on the target audience are expected to be higher if carried out by a recognized player in the sector.

- Sharing achievements: Any achievement is a great success that is worth communicating and shared among all project members, allowing it to be integrated into all the work package activities and get feed-back.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

The project meetings, the use of internal mail and the digital channels will be appropriate to get it. For external scope, the News section of the NEANIAS website and the social channels (twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn) are undoubtedly the best way to propagate good news.

- Gamification: A healthy competition among all the members is good to keep the team involved and engaged, getting the best of each one of us. The sharing of achievements of assigned KPIs by means of internal channels is a suitable option to perform it.
- Development of digital skills. The goal is to ensure that everyone working on the project can efficiently explain the project, our achievements and attract new users to the NEANIAS ecosystem using our digital channels.

3.5. Promotion of digital dissemination

As noted above, the global coronavirus pandemic strongly affected the ability to host any face-to-face events (congresses, fairs, workshops, conferences, expositions, meetings, ...). Most of them were canceled and many others went virtual.

The project faces the challenge of promoting digital channels as the most fruitful (and often the only) way to communicate and disseminate our activities and achievements. It has also been the way to obtain feedback and learn about the needs of our users and stakeholders.

We have developed and updated a digital strategy, consisting of the following key points:

- Digital engagement of NEANIAS members. Digital promotion needs digital people. The objective is to onboard all the members of the project to NEANIAS digital platforms so that they can use them to communicate, disseminate, support and establish contacts with anyone interested in the project. In this way, there is an action plan to learn, train and engage all NEANIAS members in digital media.

Figure 5. NEANIAS team interacting and promoting the project.

- Enhancement of the NEANIAS digital channels. As we are going digital, our digital channels need to be even more lively, up-to-date and interesting than initially planned. An additional effort must be done to keep NEANIAS alive, raising awareness of the project 24/7 at worldwide level.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- Promotion of NEANIAS 2.0 channels. Digital also means bidirectional. We have to open and offer our channels to everyone so that they can quote us, interact with us, send us their comments or share the content of NEANIAS with third parties. In order to reinforce this action, NEANIAS has to actively manage all the digital channels, answering the feedback. For particular events, NEANIAS will create particular e-mail addresses. For instance: OpenCall@NEANIAS.eu.
- Ecosystem engagement. A constant activity of attraction and involvement of users is needed through collaboration and participation with the ecosystem (through social networks, forums, ...) considering other projects or research centers, in order to be present, provide content and maintain the ecosystem connected and engaged.

Figure 6. NEANIAS twitter account, connecting to NEANIAS ecosystem.

- Cross promotion with synergistic projects. Participation in the social networks of other projects of interest is an additional factor for the promotion of NEANIAS, also facilitating the synergies with the environment and the identification of the project and its lines of action. Likewise, we encourage third parties to get to know us and help spread our activity.

Figure 7. Interaction with other projects and the ecosystem.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- Attendance and participation to digital events. Since many events went virtual, attendance and participation are easier, which improves the network of contacts. The involvement of NEANIAS thematic partners is necessary for identifying the most relevant events, providing the most appropriate content and representatives.

Figure 8. Online participation at congress.

- Organisation of digital events. Since it is not possible to host face-to-face events, we have to host them virtually. WP10 provides the required support and guidance to thematic work packages to accomplish this task.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 9. Promoting a NEANIAS digital event on Twitter.

- Logging of digital activities. Virtual events also mean 24 hours a day, 7 days a week and being able to consult them later and on demand. For this, a record of the contents is kept. If the reproduction rights allow for it, the videos can also be shared on our YouTube channel.

Figure 10. Events register on NEANIAS website.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- Audience profiling. Digital channels allow us to gather the audience profiles, making it easier to know them a little more, always maintaining compliance with the GDPR. Following, the subscription form to NEANIAS newsletter.

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS website's subscription form. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, NEWS, ABOUT THE SITE, and CONTACT US, along with a search bar. Below the navigation, a breadcrumb trail indicates the user's location: Home / DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS / Mailing & Newsletters / Subscribe. On the left side, there is a vertical menu with various categories such as PROJECT, About NEANIAS, Services, CONSORTIUM, ORGANIZATION, Work Plan, Management, DISSEMINATION & OPEN ACCESS, Articles & Blog, Collaboration & Research, Material, Mailing & Newsletters, Press & Media, Public outcomes, Publications, ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS & REFERENCES, EVENTS & ACTIVITIES, and OPEN CALL. The main content area is titled "Subscribe" and includes the text: "Do you want to be informed about us? Please, subscribe to NEANIAS news." Below this, there are several input fields: "Email Address" (marked as required), "First Name" (marked as required), "Last Name" (marked as required), "Organization", "Position" (marked as required), and "Website". There is also a "Fields of Interest" section with checkboxes for: Underwater Research, Atmospheric Research, Space Research, Innovative IT services and solutions, Innovation & Open Science, and Business. The "Preferred format" section has radio buttons for "HTML" (selected) and "Plain-text". The "Contact permissions" section includes a checkbox for "Newsletter / e-mail" and a small disclaimer: "By providing us with your professional data, you agree that NEANIAS may contact you through the following channels for purposes related to the project. You can check our GDPR policies on NEANIAS website." At the bottom of the form, there is a note: "You can modify the given permissions at any time on NEANIAS website. You can also unsubscribe at any time by clicking the link in the footer of our e-mails."

Figure 11. Knowing our audience: subscription form to NEANIAS newsletter.

4. Methodology

4.1. Dissemination Principles

All dissemination activities should follow some important principles:

- Respect IPR of all partners.
- Respect the work of all partners.
- Ensure the proper reference of all relevant parties whose work is directly or indirectly mentioned in the proposed publication.
- Follow transparent procedures.
- Respect confidential results and results that commercial issues arise.
- Avoid overlapping or duplication of dissemination events.
- Clearly distinguish between results suitable for dissemination and exploitable results.
- Target the right audience.
- Always mention NEANIAS project.
- Always follow the dissemination procedures.
- All content must comply with the good practices and style books about European recommendations and ethics.
- GDPR policy compliance, according the definition provided by WP10 leader.

4.2. Content generation

The creation of content must be in accordance with the target and the media. As a rule, the following must be met:

4.2.1. Presentations

Face to face and virtual events (meetings, hackathons, datathons, expositions,) must be guided by the general principles and good communication practices. In any case, each exposition may contain six main sets:

- Presentation. With the welcome of the attendees and the organization.
- Introduction. An explanation of the NEANIAS project in general lines (mainly context, goals and scope) for locating the public and the goals of the event. This introduction must be short and attractive to attendees in order to improve their attention.
- Development. This is the main section of the conference or workshop, with the main development of the topic. It is suggested to mix the theoretical concepts with some examples to get the best understanding from the audience.
- Conclusion. In this section the speaker has to remark the main concepts of the exposition, it is recommended to be brief.
- Closing. The final part when the speaker ends his presentation.
- Feedback. It is important to collect the impressions or opinions of the participants about the event carried out, as well as possible points for updates and new launches. Likewise, the contact information of the attendees and their main objectives of interest will be collected to summon them to future events, maintaining the GDPR rights.

All these points now also apply to presentations in virtual events.

4.2.2. Digital channels

Digital channels are aimed at both promoting and storing the NEANIAS news and contents. All public material will be published on the web site, which in fact acts as a content hub. Additionally, other online channels such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are also worthy of reaching out to a wide range with of short messages that inform them about news and allow them to find more information in our portal.

4.2.3. Contents of general purpose

Any general-purpose document (such as newsletters, press releases, leaflets, executive presentations, ...) is led by the Outreach Task Force with the support of the WP10 partners involved in and the final validation of Project Management Board. These documents may use any kind of content coming from other contributions to the NEANIAS scope (for instance, deliverables or specific developments may be a baseline for a newsletter) or may be specifically developed for a specific target (for instance, the promotion of an event).

4.2.4. Contents of technical purpose

The technical contents (such as whitepapers, scientific or technical contributions, webinars, code development and integrations, connections with others research lines, ...) are defined, developed and reviewed by the responsible technical partner of the relevant work package. Every partner will be responsible for the content, accuracy and correctness of every post.

4.3. Dissemination & Communication instruments

Dissemination and communication activities are carried out on two fronts: (i) at a wide range, containing mainly general contents for any kind of audience, and (ii) ecosystem, considering people involved in research or technology fields.

4.3.1. Wide range

Wide range dissemination aims to make NEANIAS known to any undetermined public as much as possible. The main instruments explaining NEANIAS goals, the work and its context, the benefits and the achievements of NEANIAS are presented below. In any case, any of them can also be useful for stakeholders.

4.3.1.1. Web site

A dedicated portal for NEANIAS (www.neanias.eu) is one of the most important channels to promote the dissemination and communication of the work performed, results and impact of ongoing project activities. The website is designed at the beginning of the activities and will be updated throughout its whole life, including updated information about the project and the consortium, news, achievements, events, downloadable material and any relevant content of interest.

The purpose of the website is to proactively promote the project and its final results by providing targeted information to various audiences within and beyond the project own community. The specific goals of this dissemination and communication channel are the following:

- To be a reference point of knowledge about the project, including scope and framework, consortium, project organization and activities.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- To be a content hub with updated with the main reports, documents, and any produced material concerning NEANIAS.
- To be a reference point for dissemination and engagement, both with its own content and through connections to other sites or platforms.
- To be a basic point of contact for anyone interested in the NEANIAS project, both from the scientific world and from the general public.

The web site has been designed considering the alignment to the defined visual identity and includes the main recommendations for the best user experience, considering accessibility, web browsing facilities, security or content organization.

The NEANIAS site is expected to attract not only the general public but also stakeholders with an interest in Underwater, Atmospheric, Space or ICT fields, and will constitute an important source of information for them, including contents for expert and non-expert audiences.

The contents will be available in the most appropriate format (formatted text, leaflets, brochures, whitepapers, news, reports, multimedia, links, ...) according to the scope and the target. Academic and technical audience (such as scientific communities, research centres, developers, or public institutions) will have the opportunity to benefit from the material published, as well as stakeholders of other European projects in order to identify synergies and potential lines of collaboration. Journalists will find updated information, such as news, events or press releases. In order to boost this media, the website includes also a useful direct link to social media platforms.

In addition, consortium and other interested and supporting stakeholders can use their own communication channels to ensure a wider dissemination and promotion of the NEANIAS project among their ranks and collaborative networks. NEANIAS will provide links to facilitate this dissemination. The website will be linked to and from the partners' website and relevant scientific communities.

The design and development of NEANIAS portal is presented in a specific deliverable belonging to the same WP10. For more information, the document "D10.2 Project Web Site" is available.

Figure 12. NEANIAS website (home page).

In the left section of the web page, the section Open Access will show all the contents organized by type (Press & Media, Material, ...).

4.3.1.2. Social media channels

Social media channels allow for reaching out to relevant groups through disseminating information about news, achievements or any relevant event in an easy and quick way. Likewise, it also allows for consolidating groups of common interests in research and ICT, empowering networking and relationships between many teams at international level.

Accessible to anyone that can be interested in NEANIAS, the social platforms address also to innovators, researchers, all relevant targeted groups. A task of followers attraction will be carried out during the whole life of the project.

The following social channels considered are LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube. In order to make it easy to find and branding the project, all of them have a common name (**neanias_eu**) and are aligned to the project identity principles. The report “D10.3 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report. Report on 1st period activities and achievements of WP10” shows all the details about the achievements of the first 18 months of the project.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

4.3.1.2.1. *LinkedIn*

In LinkedIn is created a group (www.linkedin.com/groups/13786081/) and a hashtag to promote any post (#neanias_eu).

The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 13. NEANIAS, LinkedIn group.

4.3.1.2.2. *Twitter*

An official account for NEANIAS has been created in Twitter: Neanias_eu and it is actively managed. The next figure shows the main page.

Figure 14. NEANIAS account in twitter.

4.3.1.2.3. *Facebook*

An official account for NEANIAS has been created in Facebook: Neanias_eu.

The next figure shows the main page.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 15. NEANIAS account in Facebook.

4.3.1.2.4. YouTube

An official channel for NEANIAS has been created in YouTube: Neanias_eu.

The next figure shows the main page:

Figure 16. NEANIAS channel for YouTube.

The content will be presented in different groups and playlists to help and organize access to published content. The following have been proposed:

- Demos & Training.
- NEANIAS Presentations.
- Conferences and sessions.
- Webinars.

4.3.1.3. Press releases

The press releases offer general purpose announcements and publications to the public disseminated via web site as well as electronic and printed press. This media aims to reach the widest possible audience (general public, funders and other not connected stakeholders). Collaboration with partners will be strengthened to obtain sectorial publications and in national languages.

4.3.1.4. Articles

Articles of general interest that may be distributed over the press, other media sites or the web site of the project, including project news, collaborations, outputs or achievements. Aimed to reach the general public, related initiatives, research groups or technology providers.

A coordination model has been established with all project partners to promote the publication of articles that offer thematic, sectoral and technical-scientific content.

4.3.1.5. Hardcopy, materials and gadgets

Print materials such as brochures, leaflets, cards, posters, briefing papers, or in form of different kind of gadgets that present general aspects of the project work. The goal is to strengthen project identification, consolidate engagement and to arouse the interest of the project among the most varied public. Its application will focus on face-to-face meetings, conferences, fairs and exhibitions for various audiences.

Following some examples of its use in NEANIAS meeting.

Figure 17. NEANIAS, some samples of dissemination material.

Figure 18. NEANIAS, material for project identity.

4.3.2. Ecosystem

Dissemination at ecosystem range considers any audience involved at any level or any depth with NEANIAS’s world, such as, for example, the academic or research fields, scientific or ICT context, or the above-mentioned stakeholders. This line of communication complements and expands the contents exposed widely and is backed-up by them (mainly by means of the website and the digital social media channels). The dissemination is led by the Outreach Task Force, with the participation of technical partners for content production.

The main channels include both publications and events and collaboration.

4.3.2.1. Publications

Some types of documents and channels are presented to perform the dissemination activities about NEANIAS. All documents will be hosted on the NEANIAS website and properly announced by means of News sections and social channels.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

The presented below are considered as the main ones.

4.3.2.1.1. ***Newsletters***

Periodic publications with an assembly of progresses in the project and related context (e.g. EOSC hub), mainly for EU H2020, research and innovation, and EOSC ecosystem and research groups. The newsletter production is designed by Dissemination board with the collaboration of all project members according to its area of expertise.

4.3.2.1.2. ***Mailing***

The main channels for dissemination are the digital channels and web, so we can keep and offer the communication track in an easy way. Additionally, an e-mailing service with potential additional content that notifies interested parties about progress of work of the project, mainly for targeted groups with interests (previous authorization and GDPR compliance required).

A mail list is also available for project members (h2020-neanias@cite-sa.gr).

4.3.2.1.3. ***Technical and general blog posts***

Targeted extracts technical achievements of the project that can attract the interest of specific audiences, disseminated via project's web site and social media or included in the project's newsletters. Addressed to General public, technology groups, scientific groups.

In order to achieve greater representation of all the areas and matters of NEANIAS, a coordination model has been established between all the work packages, in order to generate articles and blogs of both a generalist and sectoral and scientific type of specific interest to the ecosystem.

4.3.2.1.4. ***Whitepapers and research publications***

Some white papers that expose experiences, lessons learnt and best practices in several key areas of the project. It considers research publications in international top-rank journals and conferences in diverse fields that span Archaeology, Geology, Astrophysics, Planetary Science, Computer Science, Geoscience, Renewable Energy, Climate, and Atmospheric research. Addressed to Targeted interest groups in research, business and technology.

4.3.2.1.5. ***Multimedia material***

Material consisting of slideshows, videos or webcasts, presenting the services and their benefits disseminated via the project web site as well as social media. Addressed to research groups, technology providers.

The multimedia content is published on all NENIAS digital channels.

4.3.2.2. **Events and collaboration**

Events and collaboration ways are considered to perform the NEANIAS dissemination activities. All the events will be promoted on the NEANIAS website and properly announced through the Events & Activities sections and the social channels in order to get the maximum interest by the ecosystem, target audience and any other potential audience. Once the event already carried out, this will be announced also with the main contents and results both by the web and the social channels.

The following are considered the main ones.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

4.3.2.2.1. ***Event organization***

Organization of one general and open workshop/conference bringing together all stakeholders for the exchange of knowledge and information and evaluating the work performed, and at least 3 major thematic workshops focusing on specific areas of project activities (from research, business or technology) and several smaller scale workshops with stakeholders of interest.

4.3.2.2.2. ***Workshops, Capacity Building***

Workshops on onboarding services users, be it SMEs, Industry or researchers, bringing together those actors for raising awareness, training, assessment and feedback acquisition. Addressed to researchers and innovation stakeholders.

4.3.2.2.3. ***Fairs, Demos, Exhibitions, Conferences***

Participation in fairs and exhibitions by commercial partners presenting the business perspective of the project and its services, backed-up with hardcopy material for dissemination and engagement purposes, addressed to Service market actors.

Preliminary considerations include the presence of project with material and demonstrators in several exhibition areas, such as ICT events, EOSC/Hub events, Open Science events (ESA Open Science, Open Science Fair), RDA Plenaries, Innovation Days, and Researcher Nights. More specifically major events which will be targeted by the project are TNC2020 (GARR, part of EOSF2020), ICT 2020, and smart city events and fairs which will be useful to engage public authorities and other urban stakeholders, including research, service providers and industry: Smart City Expo World Congress, FIWARE Global Summit, IoT Week, EU Sustainable Energy Week, Zoom Smart Cities, EU Week of Regions and Cities, IoT Solutions World Congress.

4.3.2.2.4. ***Scientific publications / presentations***

Scientific publications, in a journal or conferences proceedings, including posters, and presentations. Addressed to researchers, innovators, other research and innovation stakeholders.

4.3.2.2.5. ***Open Innovation Calls***

Open calls for innovation that present the project and its offerings and attract interest for collaboration, targeting researchers, businesses and innovators to propose new services or businesses on top of NEANIAS data and service offerings. Addressed mainly to European RDI ecosystem, including also SMEs, researchers and investors.

Figure 19. First NEANIAS Open Call announcement

4.3.2.2.6. *Collaborations*

Meetings and exchanges of information with established collaborators such as projects and initiatives. Addressed to stakeholders of European innovation projects in NEANIAS's research fields and ICT industry.

4.3.2.2.7. *Datathons and Hackathons*

Datathons and hackathons will be organized in collaboration with other entities (innovation hubs, research organizations or business clusters) and will attract innovators from research and business areas, students, mentors and funders. Addressed to funders, innovators and researchers.

Figure 20. Hackathons celebrate at the Blue Days Event

4.3.2.2.8. *Project Meetings*

Project meetings will act as a communication and innovation triggering event that will be used to mobilize all partner taskforces but will also be used to introduce external actors to the project through targeted invitations from external audiences. Addressed to Project members, targeted stakeholders / liaised initiatives.

Below some figures from NEANIAS project meetings:

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 21. NEANIAS project meeting. Family photo with the old project banner.

Figure 22. NEANIAS banner welcoming the project Meeting.

Figure 23. Available material for NEANIAS project meeting.

Figure 24. NEANIAS online meetings.

4.3.3. Project resources for partners

As a main element of dissemination and communication, a set of documents will be designed in order to be used by the consortium members. The goal is to always have available digital content available for different purposes, both for new developments and for final uses. These document templates have already been provided and will be updated for the whole life of the project according the needs and will be available in the most appropriate platform according the type of use.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

The following are considered as a first batch:

Resource	Description
Word document template	Preformatted document with initial structure and look & feel as well (including pictures, tables, headings, ...) to facilitate the development of any NEANIAS related document. The structure met the needs of project deliverables but can be also suitable with particular adaptations to other NEANIAS publications (whitepapers, articles, etc.). This document is designed for project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.
Power Point document template	Preformatted document with initial structure and look & feel as well (including pictures, tables, headings, ...) to facilitate the development of any NEANIAS related presentation NEANIAS. The template also includes the promotion of NEANIAS web site and the digital social platforms. This document is designed for the project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.
Bare Brochure	Executive presentation with NEANIAS goals, services and benefits. This document is designed for the project members and will be downloadable and editable from the project platform.
Brochures and leaflets	Executive presentations with NEANIAS goals, services and benefits. These documents are designed for general audience and will be downloadable from the web site.

Table 3. Digital resources for project partners.

These documents are available on NEANIAS's SharePoint (Shared Documents\Supplementary_Templates).

As an example, a slide of kick-off meeting presentation is depicted below, which includes the logo and all the design lines of the project.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 25. NEANIAS template for presentation.

As a word document sample, this deliverable itself is an example.

And next, a sample of executive brochure introducing NEANIAS:

Figure 26. NEANIAS brochure.

4.4. Instrument per line of activity

Although all the channels can be applied for more than one line of activity (communication, dissemination, engagement and outreach), the following dedications are expected:

4.4.1. Communication instruments

The communication activities target raising awareness about the both project and its results and even reach the general public, beyond the main stakeholders identified by the project, however with proportionally smaller effort dedicated to such an audience. Many of the instruments employed for communications have a dual nature and can be utilized also for dissemination purposes, while the reverse may also apply indirectly. Several, relatively low cost, instruments that will be employed towards achieving the project communication objectives, are presented in the following:

- hardcopy materials, gadgets;
- articles;
- press releases;
- blog post;
- multimedia content;
- media extracts;
- e-mail;
- newsletter;
- social media post.

4.4.2. Dissemination instruments

Dissemination instruments can use communication instruments yet specialize on their use while, employ additional specialized instruments tailored to dissemination objectives.

The main channels are listed below:

- technical blog posts;
- whitepapers;
- multimedia material;
- workshops and capacity building;
- fairs, demos and exhibitions;
- scientific publications / presentations;
- open innovation calls;
- collaborations;
- project meetings;
- datathons and hackathons;
- social media channels.

As said above, dissemination instruments can also be useful for communication purposes.

4.5. Cross promotion

Each channel is also useful to promote others, presenting them all before the audience as a homogenous unit of work, following the principles of project identity. So that, the following rules are applied:

1. The website as a main point of reference of any contact point.

The website also offers different channels to contact and be updated about any new, as depicted below:

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 27. NEANIAS channels and contact points from the website.

2. All the channels offer the web site to the reader for any additional information. As an example is showed the link from Twitter account:

Figure 28. NEANIAS twitter account with the connection to NEANIAS website.

3. All the document templates include the reference to the site and the social channels. As an example, the last slide of a meeting presentation is depicted below:

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 29. NEANIAS presentation with references to social channels

4. The NEANIAS web and channels are also promoted from the partners and other policy makers and stakeholders' channels.

Some examples are depicted following:

Figure 30. NEANIAS reference from partner's website.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

The screenshot shows the CORDIS Europe project page for NEANIAS. The browser address bar displays "cordis.europa.eu/project/id/863448". The page header includes the CORDIS logo, the text "EU research results", a language selector set to "English", and a search bar. Below the header, there is a "Sign in" button and a navigation menu. The main content area features a "HORIZON 2020" badge and the project title "Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges". A "Fact Sheet" button is visible. The "Objective" section describes the project's goals, while the "Project information" section provides details such as the grant agreement ID (863448), start and end dates (1 November 2019 to 31 October 2022), and the overall budget (€ 5 597 025). A donut chart shows the EU contribution as € 5 597 025. The project is coordinated by ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTIRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON in Greece.

Figure 31. NEANIAS reference from CORDIS Europe.

The screenshot shows the European Open Science Cloud website. The header includes the "EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD" logo and navigation links. The main content area is titled "EOSC Portal - A gateway to information and resources in EOSC" and features a "Home" section for "NEANIAS". A date stamp "05 Nov 2019" is visible. The text describes NEANIAS as a research and innovation project under Horizon 2020. A large NEANIAS logo is prominently displayed. On the right, a "LATEST NEWS" section includes a video thumbnail and text about a Q&A session and a virtual meeting. Below the news, there is a "Call For Contributions" banner for the EOSC Symposium 2021.

Figure 32. NEANIAS reference from the European Open Science Cloud site.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

These channels are promoted from the web site, as can be seen in next image:

Figure 33. NEANIAS website and connection to other sites.

5. Organization

5.1. Coordination Model

The Outreach Task Force is created to lead and coordinate Dissemination activities. The composition of the Outreach Task Force is based on the Grant Agreement, and is led by Outreach Manager and engages partners with key roles in outreach WPs. Next chart illustrates the model.

Figure 34. Coordination model.

WP10 is composed of all project members, who are requested to contribute with their knowledge and networking, as well as the specific tasks in charge.

In order to define the contribution to each KPIs achievement, the following methodology will be applied:

Figure 35. Dissemination and KPIs assignments process.

- KPI: Presentation of all the KPIs already proposed in Grant Agreement which will define the project achievements.
- Target Value: quantification of each KPI.
- Partner share: assignment of the contribution of each partner to each KPI, according to its field of knowledge and activity.
- Partner role: role for each partner (contributor, support, ...).
- Action plan: tasks to be developed for each partner.

The contribution of each partner for each KPI has been assigned in NEANIAS digital project management tools (Redmine).

Figure 36 Redmine application

The first period of NENIAS has consolidated the need to hold different meetings that must be scheduled and organized to efficiently coordinate the activities of WP10.

5.2. Coordination activities

The Communication, Dissemination, Engagement and Dissemination WP means a cross-task throughout the life of the project that involves all partners. To lead and coordinate the activities, the WP leader has established the following means:

- WP 10 working group
- WP 10 committee
- Project meetings
- On demand meetings

5.2.1. WP 10 working group

To organize and manage the WP-10 activities, a working group has been created, made up of a representative from each partner. This group, which constitutes the executive committee of the WP 10, meets monthly, the third Friday of each month. The agenda always contains the following points:

- Overview
- Activity per WP, considering dissemination activities (already done and planned), articles and contents.
- Risks
- Dissemination activities for next month

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- KPIs status
- Next steps

Moreover, any issue is discussed considering the needs (for instance, the production of newsletter, the organization or participation in any event, collaboration with other projects and liaison activities, actions for the Open Call, legal issues, training needs, concerns, ...).

5.2.2. WP 10 Committee

To ensure that the entire project is well represented, and the workload is well balanced among all members, some tasks have been coordinated among the leaders of the NEANIAS work packages. Then, each of the WP leaders has managed internally among their members the best way to achieve the challenges purposed:

- Production of articles and contents.
- Representative content for the newsletter.
- Stakeholders' engagement.
- Collaboration with other projects.
- Participation in thematic events.
- Integration with other digital platforms.

5.2.3. Project meetings

The project meetings, both Project Management Board and the Plenary Meetings, have been very fruitful in communication, interaction, engagement and planning of actions involving WP10. They have also been a place to discuss follow-up, share achievements, and communicate general messages.

5.2.4. On demand meetings

In addition to all the above, several meetings have been held on demand in order to manage issues related to the objectives of WP. The meetings, requested by the WP-10 leader or any project member, could have been at the member level, the WP level, or with several representatives to discuss a certain matter, such as:

- KPIs discussions.
- Production of content.
- Participation in an event.
- Publishing on media.
- Analysis of contingencies.
- Stakeholder engagement.
- Networking and user attraction.
- Training needs in digital channels
- Digital resources need.
- IT integrations.
- Dissemination material needs.
- Content in other national languages.
- Joint collaboration in relevant task (open call, reports, ...)
- Etc.

5.3. Key Performance Indicator

The strategy will mainly base on the concept of Key Performance Indicator (KPI). KPIs are generally used to evaluate either the success of a particular activity or progress towards the project's goals. Choosing the right KPIs is important for the project. Although both qualitative and quantitative indicators can be used, quantitative indicators are generally preferred since they can give better insights into the project. Success indicator with each KPI will help to evaluate the success criteria for that particular KPI. The KPIs presented by this deliverable will be highly oriented towards the nature of the dissemination activities.

The following KPIs are considered, organized according main objective, considering its scope (wide range or ecosystem) and the target value:

1. KPI's concerning user (supply and demand) attraction:

Range	KPI	Target Value
Ecosystem	Workshops / conferences (co)organized	9
Ecosystem	Workshops supported by presenters and panellists on project specific topics	30

Table 4. KPIs concerning user (supply and demand) attraction.

2. KPIs concerning innovation dissemination:

Range	KPI	Target Value
Ecosystem	Open calls applicants/ participants	30

Table 5. KPIs concerning innovation dissemination.

3. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination:

Range	KPI	Target Value
Wide range	Average social media posts per month	8
Wide range	General public articles languages supported	9
Ecosystem	Peer reviewed scientific publications	6
Ecosystem	Other scientific publications and artefacts	30
Ecosystem	References and acknowledgements	100
Ecosystem	Whitepapers (as per work plan)	4
Ecosystem	Multimedia & training material published	30

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Ecosystem	Gold open access publications percentage	30%
Wide range	Fairs and exhibitions participated	20
Wide range	Commercial exploitation events participation	10

Table 6. KPIs concerning scientific dissemination.

4. KPIs concerning social dissemination:

Range	KPI	Target Value
Wide range	Websites launched (work plan)	1
Wide range	Website content updating (average)	weekly
Ecosystem	Templates for dissemination activities and other premade dissemination material	10
Ecosystem	Hardcopy/tangible material forms	5
Wide range	Social media dissemination channels	4
Wide range	Social media impressions (social media channels total)	30.000
Wide range	Social media followers (total across media)	2.000
Wide range	Average technical blog posts per month	4
Wide range	Average general public blog posts per month	4
Wide range	General public articles on printed or online media	30
Wide range	Newsletters issued (biannual)	6

Table 7. KPIs concerning social dissemination.

5. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts:

Range	KPI	Target Value
Ecosystem	Relevant H2020 Projects & research infrastructures liaised with NEANIAS (total)	20
Ecosystem	Projects & initiatives liaised with, from the same call, sharing experiences and solutions to challenges	3 (all)
Ecosystem	MoUs signed with 3rd parties	10

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons organized by the project	4
Ecosystem	3rd party Datathons/hackathons supported by the project	4
Ecosystem	Datathons/hackathons participants	500
Ecosystem	Individuals directly addressed via scientific, academic communication, innovation stimulation, training and engagement activities	3.000

Table 8. KPIs concerning strengthen impact via joint efforts.

Responding to the maturity of the project, a higher incidence of these KPIs is expected in the second half of the project, when contacts and dissemination are more consolidated, and the project can offer more tangible results.

5.4. Roles

Outreach Task Force (OTF): Outreach task force is led by Outreach Manager and engages partners with key roles in outreach WPs. The role of the team is to monitor outreach activities, identify opportunities and mobilise resources, as outreach in NEANIAS is quite intensive, ambitious and of strategic importance for the success of the project.

5.5. Monitoring and Evaluation

5.5.1. Digital channels

The web page will be regularly updated. Moreover, the effectiveness of the web page will be periodically analysed by means of the Google Analytics tool. This will allow reports to run on the website, giving a very clear picture of information such as:

- Users count visiting the website and visit time.
- Languages and locations of visitors.
- Devices used for browsing the website.

The social channels will be also periodically tracked by means of embedded tools in each platform.

Following an example from Facebook account, tracking the impressions among others KPIs (similar will be applied for the others social networks):

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Figure 37. NEANIAS Facebook account: tracking facilities (example).

5.5.2. Physical channels

The tracking from physical channels (meetings, published articles, connections with other projects, events hosted and attendees, ...) will be collected for each specific action and monthly updated and shared at internal level, analysing the level of fulfilment and trends, being useful for the committed project reports. This will be used also for gamification purposes.

NEANIAS Outreach Task Force members list is the following:

Member	Partner	Committee Role
Daniel Martínez	RICOH	Outreach Manager
Jordi Sala	RICOH	Outreach Manager deputy
Eleni Petra	NKUA	Member
Konstantinos Karantzalos	ATHENA	Member
Filomena Bufano	INAF	Member
Robert Lovas	SZTAKI	Member
Kalliopi Baika	AMU	Member
Giuseppe Vizzari	UNIMIB	Member
Angelo Pio Rossi	JUCOBSUNI	Member
Katalin Kovacs	INNOMINE	Member
Claudio Pisa	GARR	Member
Olga Sidiropoulou	CITE	Member

Table 9. Outreach Task Force members.

5.5.3. Reporting models

A set of templates for reporting dissemination will be created, according each kind of publication. The content of each one will meet the needs of any specific kind of action.

1. Scientific publications:
 - Type of scientific publication (article in Journal, publication in conference proceedings / workshops, books/ chapter in books, thesis/dissertation, others).
 - Title of scientific publication.
 - Digital Object Identifier (DOI).
 - ISSN or eSSN.
 - Author(s).
 - Title of the journal or equivalent.
 - Number/ date.
 - Publisher.
 - Place of publication.
 - Year of public action.
 - Pages.
 - Public & private publication.
 - Peer view.
 - Is/will open access provided to this publication.
2. General publications (press releases, videos, campaigns etc.):
 - Type of publication (press release, non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications, flyers, social media, website, communication campaign, video/film, others).
 - Title of publication.
 - Author(s)/ creator (s).
 - Title of the journal or equivalent.
 - Date of publication.
 - Publisher - Partner.
 - Place of publication.
 - Public & private publication.
 - Is/Will open access provided to this publication.
 - Other relevant comments.
3. Dissemination and communication activities:
 - Type of dissemination and communication activities (organization of a conference, organization of a workshop, project presentations, exhibition, training, participation to a conference/ a workshop/ or other event, brokerage/ pitch/ trade fair, others).
 - Title of activity.
 - Short description.
 - Website/ social media (if available).
 - Type of audience.
 - Number of attendees.
 - Date of the activity.

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

- Place of the activity.
 - Partner participants (name, affiliation).
 - Presentation if applicable.
 - Is/will open access provided to this publication.
 - Other comments.
4. Dissemination and communication results:
- Type of audience reached in the context of all dissemination & communication activities (multiple choices are possible among science community/ higher education, research, industry, civil society, general public, policy makers, media, investors, others).
 - Estimated number of persons reached.

6. Planning

Project kick-off is the launch of dissemination activities, meaning the first generation of templates and organization of committees.

6.1. Deliverables Description

The deliverables of this WP are detailed below, specifying its codification, title and description:

- D10.1 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft), report on vision, strategy, and draft plan of opportunities, targets and outcomes expected and baseline dissemination material – regularly updated after delivery.
- D10.2 Project web site, site with visual alignment to the strategy with initial content.
- D10.3 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report, report on 1st period activities and achievements of WP.
- D10.4 Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final), updated / final strategy and activity plan.
- D10.5 NEANIAS open event, execution of one open event on NEANIAS (delivery up to 2 months after the date start).
- D10.6 Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report, summarizing all activities performed by WP and partners the results and feedback obtained by their audience / counterparts

6.2. Deliverables Planning

Finally, the scheduling for deliverables is presented in the following table:

Code	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Month
D10.1	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Draft)	RICOH	Report	Public	2
D10.2	Project web site	RICOH	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	2
D10.3	Dissemination, outreach and liaison activities report	RICOH	Report	Public	18
D10.4	Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)	RICOH	Report	Public	18
D10.5	NEANIAS open event	RICOH	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	32
D10.6	NEANIAS open event	RICOH	Report	Public	36

D10.4. Communication, Dissemination, Outreach and Engagement Plan (Final)

Table 10. Dissemination planning.

6.3. Timeline

The timeline of activities and due dates is depicted below.

Figure 38. Timeline

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OTF	Outreach task force
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web